

Project 539369-LLP-1-2013-1-ES-ERASMUS-ENW

Start: 1.10.2013

Duration: 36 months

Funded with the support from the European Commission.

OIKONET A global multidisciplinary network on housing research and learning

Deliverable 5.4

Upgrade of the Virtual Campus platform

Revision: 5

Due date: 2015-03-31 (m18)

Lead partner: LA SALLE (FUNITEC)

This project is funded with support from the European Commission (Project number 539369-LLP1-2013-1-ES-ERASMUS-ENW). This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Deliverable Administration and Summary

No & name	Deliverable 5.4 Upgrade of the Virtual Campus platform				
Status	Final	Due	M18 (2015-03-31)	Final version	2017-02-28
Author(s)	Leandro Madrazo, Marta Salgado, Marcos Segovia, David Ortiz (LA SALLE)				
Editor	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)				
Work Programme Description	Upgrade of the existing OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus environments (Workspaces, Case Repository, Oikopedia) to adapt them to the needs of the OIKONET pedagogical activities.				
Comments	A previous version of this document was submitted along with the interim report, in April 2015.				

Document history

V	Date	Author	Description
1	2015-02-03	David Ortiz (LA SALLE)	Automatic emailing function to report users about the insertion of comments to students works.
2	2015-03-15	Marcos Segovia (LA SALLE)	Description of the improvements that were implemented in Workspaces
3	2015-03-15	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)	Integration of texts in the document, completing executive summary and conclusions
4	2016-04-16	Leandro Madrazo (LA SALLE)	Upgrade with latest improvements after interim report; final editing and reviewing
5	2016-04-18	Lisa Kinnear (LA SALLE)	Final proof-reading

Table of Contents

1 Executive Summary	3
2 Introduction	4
2.1 Purpose and target group	4
2.2 Contribution of partners	4
2.3 Relations to other activities in the project	4
3 Upgraded Oikodomos Workspaces	5
3.1 Design development process	5
3.2 Implemented improvements	9
3.2.1 Workspaces home page.....	9
3.2.2 Enhanced contents in entry page.....	10
3.2.3 Enhanced Calendar tool	10
3.2.4 Automatic messaging	11
3.2.5 Workspace home page	12
3.2.6 Technical implementation.....	14
4 Upgraded Oikopedia	15
5 Thinking Dwelling.....	17
6 Conclusions.....	25

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This is a report of the enhancements in the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus, previously developed between 2007 to 2009 by the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle. Since then, the environment has remained operational under the maintenance of the developer team. The improvements have focused on two of the learning environments of the virtual campus: OIKODOMOS Workspaces and Oikopedia. The enhancements have been made following the requests formulated by users of the virtual campus environments in the OIKONET project.

In addition, a full-fledged web-based learning environment has been added to the existing virtual campus: Thinking Dwelling. This environment supports the collaboration of learners – students and teachers- across the courses and seminars taking place at each OIKONET partner institution dealing with contemporary housing issues.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

This report summarizes the enhancements done in the OIKODOMOS Workspaces environment to facilitate its use in the OIKONET project. The upgrades reported have been discussed within the Consortium, specifically with the members of the subnetwork Pedagogical Activities who are the users of this tool. The work reported in the document might be of interest to educational technologists with a focus on Learning Management Systems.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The enhancements have been performed by the research team ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle, the developer of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus tools. Members of the subnetwork Pedagogical Activities have provided their feedback as users of the environment, and have participated in the discussions preceding the upgrade of the Workspaces environment.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

OIKODOMOS Workspaces is being used to design and implement the learning spaces carried out in WP4 Pedagogical Activities. Therefore, it is an essential component of the pedagogical work being done in the OIKONET project.

3 UPGRADED OIKODOMOS WORKSPACES

After using OIKODOMOS Workspaces in the different learning spaces implemented in the academic year 2013-14 (see Deliverable 4.1), OIKONET partners identified some aspects to be improved as well as some missing functionalities in the current version of the learning environment. Their feedback was collected at the end of the academic year. In the fall semester of 2014-15, the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus developer –the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture La Salle– elaborated a proposal to upgrade the Workspaces learning environment. This proposal was circulated among partners to get their feedback. After several iterations, a series of improvements was agreed to be implemented. The upgrade version has been operative since the start of the spring semester 2014-15.

The improvements focused on the following aspects:

- making more visible the activities being carried out within each learning space in the home pages . This was necessary particularly for external users who could not see in the existing home page what was being done in the learning space, without being registered.
- creating a separate home page for each learning space. This was necessary, particularly because several learning spaces were active simultaneously.
- facilitating the use of existing communication tools included in Workspaces, such as the Calendar and the Bulletin Board. These tools were too hidden to the user and, therefore, were not used properly.
- informing registered users about the activity in the learning space. This was necessary to inform registered users about the latest information introduced in the Workspace, for instance, a new comment to a student work or a new task.

3.1 Design development process

Figure 1 shows the changes proposed to upgrade Workspaces with a specific home page for each learning space. In the previous version, all the information about the on-going learning spaces was concentrated in one single page (Figure 1). In this way, it was not possible to have an overview of what was being done in the learning space.

PROBLEMS WITH THE CURRENT VERSION

Figure 1. Limitations of the current OIKODOMOS home page

With the proposed solution, each learning space has its own home page, and a unique URL to access it (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Proposal to create a new home page specific to each Workspace

A proposal was made to redefine the contents of the existing homepage of OIKODOMOS Workspaces (Figure 3) and for the new home pages specific to a Workspace (Figure 4). Before implementing them, the proposals were sent to partners to get their feedback.

Figure 3. Mock-up of the layout and content of the Workspace home page

Figure 4. Mock-up of the layout and content of the Workspace home page

3.2 Implemented improvements

After receiving the feedback of partners, the agreed solutions were implemented. In particular, the following improvements have been made:

- Modification of contents of the OIKODOMOS Workspaces home page, making visible the inputs of all Bulletin Boards of all active Workspaces, and moving the learning structure to the new home page of each Workspace
- Enhancement the contents of the entry page of each Workspace with new information obtained from the Calendar tool, including access to the activities reports
- Improvement of the Calendar tool, generating a list of planned events which is displayed in different views
- Addition of a functionality to receive automatic emails informing about the system's activity
- Creation of a new home page to each Workspace, specifically

3.2.1 Workspaces home page

Figure 5 shows the implemented changes in the current version of the Workspaces. The registration can be done in this home page or, alternatively, selecting >Access in a particular Workspace.

Figure 5. Changes implemented in the Workspaces home page

3.2.2 Enhanced contents in entry page

The entry page includes now two new text boxes at the bottom of the log box (Figure 6): a list of the latest events planned in the Calendar tool and a list of the activity reports (typically, documents summarizing the work done in the learning space until a certain point, reported by the coordinator of the learning space).

Figure 6. Changes implemented in the Workspaces home page

3.2.3 Enhanced Calendar tool

A list summarizing the events planned each month is now shown at the bottom of the Calendar (Figure 7). This provides a quick view of the activities that are going to take place each month. The list is also shown in the entry page of the Workspace, as well as in the public home page of each Workspace (see Section 3.2.4).

Figure 7. Changes implemented in the Workspaces home page

3.2.4 Automatic messaging

The user is notified when some actions are performed in the workspace, for example, when another user introduces a comment, or when a teacher evaluates a deliverable.

By default, the notifications service is enabled. They can be disabled in the user profile page view, accessible in the Participants menu (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Added functionality to receive messages about the activities in the Workspace

The notifications are sent to the e-mail account of the registered user. Users are notified in the following cases:

- when a user comments a work submitted by a student: the student who submitted the work receives a notification

- when a user comments the work done by a group of students in a task: all users that are in the group task will receive the notification.
- when a teacher evaluates the work submitted by a student: the student who submitted the work, receives a notification.
- when a teacher creates a new learning activity: users with a teacher profile who are participating in the Workspace receive a notification.

3.2.5 Workspace home page

The contents of the Workspace home page are structured in three tabs: Home, Learning Activities, and Calendar. This information is available to the non-registered user accessing this page. In this way, they can understand the learning structure and understand the context of the works done by students.

The left section of the Home page shows a selection of relevant student works, links to social web tools used in the learning space (e.g. Facebook, blogs), a short list of the planned events (introduced through the enhanced Calendar tool), and a list of the activity reports. In the right side, there is the Bulletin Board with the logs of the learning space activity, and (if available) an embedded Twitter channel informing to the public about the work being done (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Mock-up of the layout and content of the implemented Workspace home page

Learning Activities shows the structure of learning activities and tasks, as well as the works submitted by students (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Unfolded structure of learning activities, tasks and student works

The tab calendar shows the list of the planned events, introduced using the Calendar tool in the learning space (Figure 11).

Figure 11. List of planned events

3.2.6 Technical implementation

OIKODOMOS Workspaces was developed with the CakePHP framework which follows the pattern model-view-controller. Most of the improvements reported above have been implemented at the view level (i.e. interface level). However, some of the changes introduced in the existing software required of deeper changes such as the automatic messaging service. In this case, new functions have been implemented in the controller “users_controller.php”:

- *send_mail_comment_deliverable*: This function is responsible for sending the notification when a user introduces a comment to a student work. The notification is sent to the user who submits the deliverable.
- *send_mail_comment_task*: This function sends a notification when a user introduces a comment to the works done by a group of students in a task. The notification is sent to all users that are part of the group
- *send_mail_deliverable_evaluation*: This function sends the notifications when a teacher evaluates a student work. The notification is sent to the student who submits the work
- *send_mail_new_activity*: This function sends the notifications when a teacher creates a learning activity in the Workspace. The notifications are sent to all teachers participating in the Workspace

There were problems to implement the mailing service inside the CakePHP framework, mainly because the framework used to write the code is outdated (CakePHP framework which version was 1.3.16 and at the moment of writing the version was 3.0.1). For this reason, the mail service has been implemented as a script outside of the framework. The functions described above set the variables and then call the script in order to send the mail.

4 UPGRADED OIKOPEDIA

The menus of the Oikopedia environments have been enhanced to improve the readability of the concept list and to facilitate the navigation of contents in different languages. In the existing environment, developed in a previous OIKODOMOS project, the concepts were alphabetically listed and the option to select the language of the content was hidden in a pull-down menu (Figure 12).

The screenshot shows the OIKOpedia interface. On the left, a vertical list of concepts is displayed under the heading 'Concept'. The 'Capacity-building' concept is selected. On the right, the detailed view for 'Capacity-building' is shown, including its introduction, a paragraph of text, a 'Related Cases' section with a thumbnail, and a 'References' section with a list of sources. A language dropdown menu is visible at the top right, set to 'English'.

Figure 12. Previous version of Oikopedia

As the number of concepts increased with the addition of new ones, it became necessary to structure the list by blocks, each one starting in a letter of the alphabet. This facilitates the identification of a concept. Likewise, for a selected concept the available versions in other languages appear as a submenu under the concept name in the main window. This makes it easier to know: 1. if there is a version of the content in other languages and 2. to select the desired language (Figures 13, 14).

Figure 13. Previous version of Oikopedia

Figure 14. Improved menus

5 THINKING DWELLING

A new web-based environment (www.oikonet.org/thinking_dwelling) has been specifically created for the learning space “Thinking Dwelling” (see Deliverable 4.1 “Learning Space”). The objective of “Thinking Dwelling” is to encourage students and teachers of architecture –of all courses and levels– to reflect on the forms of dwelling in our global societies and to develop a critical understanding which enables them to envision the role of the architect in the shaping of the spaces we inhabit. The web environment enables participants to share their reflections structured around three themes:

- Representing. To provide examples of ways of living through different art forms. For example, the relationship between inhabitants and space expressed in a film scene, a painting, a photograph, a passage of book, a piece of music...
- Experiencing. To express the relationships with the spaces we live in, using any form of representation: a drawing, a video, a photograph, a text, a sound, in any combination.
- Projecting. To collect personal experiences about renowned houses, to comment on relevant examples of housing design.

The web-based environment has been implemented in PHP using the development framework CodeIgniter (www.codeigniter.com). The front-end interface has been implemented in HTML, CSS and Javascript. It has been developed in two stages: a fully operative version was completed in September 2015 and used during the academic year 2015/16; an improved version, with new functionalities (creating groups, adding comments, summarizing user’s contributions, restricted access with login, and improved navigation) was released in September 2016.

The functionalities of this web-based environment are described next.

- **Home (public).** There is a home page available to all interested users which describes the objectives of the learning space. In the right side, the latest contributions are displayed in the different social media channels (Instagram, Twitter, YouTube) (Figure 15). Users need to register to be able to submit their works and to have access to the work of other users (Figure 16). Registered users need to login to access to the contents of the learning space.

Figure 15. Registration form

Figure 16. Registration form

- **Home (registered user).** The entry page for registered users is structured in three areas: 1. Recent activities, where the latest submissions are displayed with images 2. Latest events, a list of the conferences, lectures and presentations in the participating institutions and 3. Dissemination of the activities in the social media (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Public home page

The menu of the learning environment is structured in: Programs, Activities, Participants and Guidelines.

- **Programs.** It contains the list of partner organizations which are participant in the activities. For each institution in the list, there is a document describing the activities that are being carried out in connection with the “Thinking Dwelling” programme (Figure 18).

The screenshot displays the 'THINKING DWELLING' website interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'HOME', 'PROGRAMS', 'ACTIVITIES', 'PARTICIPANTS', 'GUIDELINES', and 'CONTACT'. The 'PROGRAMS' section is active, listing several participating institutions:

- laSalle ARO** (Universidad Hispano-Española): School of Architecture La Salle - 2016/17. A program of activities associated to THINKING DWELLING will be carried out from 14th to 30th September 2016.
- UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE PUERTO RICO**: Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico. A program of activities associated to THINKING DWELLING will be carried out from 18th to 25th May 2016.
- ESCOLA TÉCNICA SUPERIOR D'ARQUITECTURA**: Technical School of Architecture of V. A program of activities associated to THINKING DWELLING will be carried out from 18th to 25th May 2016.
- İTÜ** (İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi): Istanbul Technical University - Facult 2015/16. A program of activities associated to THINKING DWELLING will be carried out from 18th to 25th May 2016.
- UNIVERSITÉ Grenoble Alpes**: Institut d'urbanisme. A program of activities related to THINKING DWELLING will be carried out from 18th to 25th May 2016.
- KU LEUVEN LUCA**: KU Leuven - Faculteit Architectuur - 2. A program of activities connected to THINKING DWELLING will be carried out from 18th to 25th May 2016.
- laSalle ARO**: School of Architecture La Salle - 2016. The program THINKING DWELLING will run at the S. The program includes debates and presentations to be carried out at the school, in parallel to the on-line activities.

On the right side, there is an 'INSTAGRAM' section with a grid of images. Below the institution list, a large banner features the 'THINKING DWELLING' logo, the dates '18 April – 25 May 2016', and the 'Polytechnic University of Puerto Rico' logo. A 'PROGRAM' section follows, detailing the schedule:

PROGRAM

WEEK 1 (18 APR)

MONDAY 18 08.30 PM / AUDITORIUM PUPP
LABORATORY: KNOWING RESEARCH TOOLS AND DEFINING A RESEARCH PROBLEM

WEDNESDAY 20 08.30 PM / AUDITORIUM PUPP
LABORATORY: KNOWING RESEARCH TOOLS AND DEFINING A RESEARCH PROBLEM

WEEK 2 (05 APR)

MONDAY 21 08.30 PM / AUDITORIUM PUPP
SESSION OF CRITIQUES ON WRITING SKILLS AND VIDEO EDITING

WEDNESDAY 23 08.30 PM / AUDITORIUM PUPP
SESSION OF CRITIQUES ON WRITING SKILLS AND VIDEO EDITING

Figure 18. Participating institutions

- **Activities.** It contains the contributions of learners – students and tutors– to the three activities – Representing, Experiencing and Projecting–. They can be filtered in various ways: by partner, tag, user and program (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Activities filtered by tag

By clicking on the image of a submission, a detailed view of the work is. Users can leave their comments about the work of another users. Also, the groups to which the work has been related are displayed (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Detailed view of a submitted work

To gather the contents submitted by all users in groups, it is necessary to select them and then give a name and a description to the group. This action takes place on the right side window (Figure 21).

Figure 21. Group creation

To submit a work for one of the three activities, the user needs to select first the activity and the use “Upload Activity” (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Form to upload a work for an activity

- **Participants.** It shows all participants in the various editions of the learning space. They can be filtered by partner and by user name (Figure 23). After selecting a participant, a view of the work carried out by the user is displayed (Figure 24). Similar results can be obtained by clicking on the name of the logged user. In this case, the work of the registered user is shown.

Figure 23. View of participants

Figure 24. Form to upload a work for an activity

- **Guidelines.** A concise expansion of the features and functionalities of the environment, to help users working with it (Figure 25).

Figure 25. View of the guidelines

6 CONCLUSIONS

Improvements made in the existing OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus – Workspaces, Oikopedia – have contributed to enhance the user experience, and to better communicate –with registered user and with external users– the work being done in the learning spaces carried out during the project (see Deliverable 5.1 “Learning Spaces”). However, implementing these changes have required a considerable time because of the difficulties to work with a programming environment which is outdated after being ten years in operation. In the light of these difficulties, the developing team is considering different options to redo the Workspaces environment, either updating the version of the programming framework or translating the source code to a new one.

A new web-based learning environment has been created from scratch to foster the collaboration among partner institutions. The use of this environment by participants from various institutions has proofed that it is straightforward to work with. The latest functionalities that have been added in its second release (creating groups, adding comments) can help to make this environment a repository of learning resources which can be used in multiple ways in the courses taking place at the participating schools.